

IMPACT OF PRICES ON COTTON IN VIDARBHA

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Abstract

The present study was undertaken in Vidarbha region. The cotton crop was selected for the present study. The data were collected on area, production, productivity of cotton grown in Vidarbha region pertaining to the period from 2001- 2002 to 2020-2021 (20 years) For the analysis of growth and instability, the entire study period was split into two sub- periods and overall. The district-wise time series data on area, production, productivity and various prices were collected from Government publication and websites. The compound growth rates of area, production and productivity of Cotton, estimated for last 20 years. To measure the instability in area, production and productivity, an index of instability was used as a measure of variability through Coefficient of Variation (CV) and Cuddy Della Valle's instability indices. To measure the relative contribution of area, yield to the total output of the Paddy crop, Minhas (1964), Decomposition analysis model was used. The impact of various prices on area was estimated with the help of Narlovian -Lagged Model. At overall level the compound growth rate of area of cotton for Vidarbha region is positive and significant. The compound growth rate of production of cotton is positive and significant at overall level for Vidarbha region. At overall level for Vidarbha region area, the CDVII 3.25 per cent instability. At overall level for Vidarbha region production Vidarbha recorded 4.80 per cent instability. At overall level for Vidarbha region productivity, Vidarbha recorded 2.68 per cent instability Vidarbha as a whole yield effect is most responsible factor for change in cotton production i.e. 91.66 per cent whereas area effect and interaction effect were 2.9 per cent and 5.46 per cent respectively.

Keywords - cotton crop, productivity, Coefficient of Variation.

Introduction and Objectives

Cotton widely known as "White Gold" is a major commercial crop and is having global significance for its lint and seed. Cotton is an important cash crop in many developing countries supporting the livelihoods of millions of poor households.

Total area of cotton in Vidarbha region were 16.98 lakh hectare and production were 38.94, lakh, tonnes. The agricultural prices commission (APC) was set up in India in 1965 to advice the government on evolving a valence and integrated price structure. The policy framework was modified in 1980, when the emphasis was shifted on tot the balance between demand and foodgrain minimum support price (MSP) is a form of market intervention by the government of India to insure agricultural producers against any sharp fall in form prices. The MSP are announced by the government of India at a beginning of the sowing season for certain crops on the basis of the recommendation of the CACP. MSPs are prices fixed by government of India to protect the producer-farmers-against excessive fall in price during bumper production years. The MSP are the guarantee price for their produce from the government. If there is a fall in the prices of the crops, after a bumper harvest, the government purchases at the MSP and this is the reason that price cannot be below MSP so this directly help the farmers. Such minimum MSP are fixed at incentive level, so as to induce the farmers to make capital investment for the improvement of their farm and to motivate them to adapt improve crop production technologies to step up their production and there by income.

The farm harvest prices(FHP) are those which is prevail during a six to eight weeks immediately after the harvesting period and wholesale prices are those which prevail in the wholesale markets. Through, there are some years in between when the wholesale prices have fallen below FHP, on an average of kind of pattern observed is – support price < Farm Harvest Price< Wholesale Price,the farm harvest prices capital and WSP of selected major crops are weighted averages

WSP accordingly is the rate at which a relatively large transaction, generally for further sale, is effected price policy for agric-produce is to set remunerative prices with a view to encourage higher investment and production.

If recent year, the MSP policy has been criticized by both farmers and proponents of free trade. Farmer always demand a substantial hike in MSP, whereas profree agricultural trade thinkers feel that, most of the

times, MSP is in a line with the international prices as well as domestic demand and supply situation. This brings distortions and inefficiency in production pattern.If there is a fall in the prices of the crops, the government purchase at the MSP and this is reason that the priced cannot be below MSP.In the absence of such a guaranteed price, there is a concern that farmer may shift to other crops causing shortage in this commodities.

The agricultural price policy (MSP) has outlived its utility and is being used more as a political tool than an economic tool. Therefore, it becomes imperative to examine the effectiveness of MSP in different regions of the country as well as its contribution towards growth. Since MSP policy is consider to have approved mostly the surplus states, its role and contribution towards production was examined for the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra state. Therefore this study was planned with the following specific objectives

- 1) To estimate the growth and instability of cotton.
- 2) To measure the relative contribution of area, yield to the total output .
- 3) To study the impact of various prices on area

Methodology:

The present study was undertaken in Vidarbha region. The data were collected on area, production, productivity of Cotton in Vidarbha region pertaining to the period from 2001-2002 to 2020-2021 (20 years) For the analysis of growth and instability, the entire study period was split into two sub-periods and overall as follows.

Period I	: 2001-2002 to 2010-2011
Period II	: 2011-2012 to 2020-2021
Overall	: 2001-2002 to 2020-2021

Source of data

The district-wise time series data on area, production, productivity and various prices were collected from Government publication and websites

Growth rate

The compound growth rates of area, production and productivity of Cotton.were estimated for last 20 years. The district wise compound growth rates of area, production and productivity were estimated by using following exponential model.

$$Y = a.b^t \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where,

Y = Depended variable for which growth rate is to be estimated
 a = Intercept
 b = Regression Coefficient
 t = Time Variable
 This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows
 $\text{Log } y = \log a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots\dots (2)$
 Then the per cent compound growth rate (g) was computed using the relationship.
 $\text{CGR } (r) = [\text{Antilog } (\log b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (3)$
 The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test.

Instability

To measure the instability in area, production and productivity, an index of instability was used as a measure of variability through Coefficient of Variation (CV) and Cuddy Della Valle's instability indices.

Coefficient of variation (CV)

$$\text{CV } (\%) = \frac{\sigma}{X} \times 100$$

Where,
 σ = Standard deviation
 X = Arithmetic mean

The simple Coefficient of Variation (C.V) often contains the trend component and thus over estimates the level of instability in time series data characterized by long term trends and Cuddy Della Valle's instability was estimated as follows.

Cuddy Della Valle's Instability Indices (CDVI)

It was used to measure instability of paddy, cotton & soybean which was close to approximation of the average year to year per cent variation adjusted for trend. The algebraic form of it was;
 Instability Index = $\text{CV} \sqrt{1-R^2}$

Where,
 CV = Simple Estimates of coefficient of variation in per cent and
 R^2 = Coefficient of determination from a time trend regression (linear) adjusted by the number of degree of freedom.

Decomposition of output growth

To measure the relative contribution of area, yield to the total output of the Cotton., Soybean and Paddy crop, Minhas (1964), Decomposition analysis model was used which is given below.

$P_o = A_o \times Y_o$ and
 $P_n = A_n \times Y_n \dots\dots\dots (1)$
 A_o, P_o and Y_o are area, production and productivity in base year and A_n, P_n and Y_n are values of the respective variable in nth year item respectively.

Where,
 A_o and A_n = Area
 Y_o and Y_n = yield in the base year and nth year respectively.

$$P_n - P_o = \Delta P$$

$$A_n - A_o = \Delta A$$

$$Y_n - Y_o = \Delta Y \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

For equation (1) and (2) we can write
 $P_o + \Delta P = (A_o + \Delta A) (Y_o + \Delta Y)$
 Hence,

$$P = \frac{A_o \Delta Y}{\Delta P} \times 100 + \frac{Y_o \Delta A}{\Delta P} \times 100 + \frac{\Delta Y \Delta A}{\Delta P} \times 100$$

Production = Yield effect + area effect + interaction effect
 Thus, the total change in production can be decomposed into yield effect area effect and the interaction effect due to change in yield and area.

The impact of various prices on area and production was estimated with the help of Narlovian -Lagged Model.

$$A_t = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + b_5 X_5 + b_6 X_6 + b_7 X_7$$

Where
 A_t = Current year area under Cotton / Soybean/ Paddy
 X_1 = One year lagged area of Cotton/Soybean/Paddy
 X_2 = One year lagged Farm Harvest Prices of Cotton / Soybean/ Paddy
 X_3 = Current year Minimum Support Prices of Cotton / Soybean/ Paddy
 X_4 = One year lagged Wholesale prices of Cotton / Soybean/ Paddy
 X_5 = Farm Harvest Price risk of Cotton / Soybean/ Paddy
 X_6 = Minimum Support Price risk of Cotton / Soybean/ Paddy
 X_7 = Wholesale Price risk of Cotton / Soybean/ Paddy
 X_8 = Yield risk of Cotton / Soybean/ Paddy
 b_1 to b_7 = Coefficient
 R^2 = Coefficient of determination

Result And Discussion

The district wise compound growth rates of area of cotton crop in Vidarbha during 2001-02 to 2020-21 was shown in below Table 1.

Table 1:-Growth rates of area of cotton in different districts of Vidarbha (2001-02 to 2020-21)

Districts	Period-I	Period-II	Overall
Buldhana	3.72**	-3.06	-0.62
Akola	-3.95**	-0.07	-2.14**
Washim	-6.39**	-11.13*	-8.81**
Amravati	-7.43**	4.21**	-0.85
Yavatmal	0.98	0.45	1.22**
Amravati Division	-1.55	0.02	-0.59
Wardha	-0.24	4.75**	5.88**
Nagpur	-2.47	-2.42	5.88
Bhandara	-	-	-
Gondia	-	-	-
Chandrapur	1.95	5.46**	8.06**
Gadchiroli	-	-	-
Nagpur Division	-0.18	1.63**	6.23**
Vidarbha	-1.21	6.77	1.06*

Note: ** Significance at 1 % level, * significance 5% level.

The Table 1 revealed that, for period I area of cotton was negative and non significant for Amravati and Nagpur division. As for as Vidarbha as a whole is concerned the area under cotton was negative & non significant. In period II Amravati, Yavatmal, Wardha, Chandrapur and Vidarbha region shows positive growth rate of Cotton. At overall 20 years the compound growth rate of area for cotton was positive and

significant for Yavatmal (1.22 per cent), Wardha (5.88 per cent), Chandrapur (8.06 per cent), and Vidarbha region (1.06 per cent) where as growth rate of area for Washim and Akola district was negatively significant. The district wise compound growth rates in Vidarbha during 2001-02 to 2020-21 was shown in Table 2.

Table 2-Growth rates of production of cotton production in different districts in Vidarbha (2001-02 to 2020-21).

Districts	Period-I	Period-II	Overall
Buldhana	11.81**	-2.15	1.04
Akola	6.47	4.51	2.78
Washim	2.33	-4.63	-4.95*
Amravati	2.90	6.03	5.97**
Yavatmal	12.33**	-0.09	4.09*
Amravati Division	8.79*	1.64	3.39*
Wardha	4.23	12.61*	11.13**
Nagpur	1.80	16.33**	10.31**
Bhandara	-	-	-
Gondia	-	-	-
Chandrapur	11.45**	10.06*	13.82**
Gadchiroli	-	-	-
Nagpur Division	5.25	12.83**	11.54**
Vidarbha	8.18**	5.34	5.74**

Note: ** Significance at 1 % level, * significance 5% level.

It could be seen from Table 2 that, during period I, the growth rate of production was highest in Yavatmal (12.33 per cent), Buldhana(11.81 per cent), and Chandrapur (11.45 per cent) respectively. As for as Vidarbha is concerned the growth rate of production under cotton was positive (8.18 per cent) & significant at 1 % level. During Period II the growth rate of cotton production was highest in Nagpur district (16.33 per cent) followed by Wardha district (12.61 per cent) and for Chandrapur district (10.06 per cent) and it was found significant. As for as Vidarbha is concerned the growth rate of production under cotton

was positive (5.34 per cent) but non significant. At overall 20 years the compound growth rate of production for cotton was positive and significant for Chandrapur (13.82 per cent), Wardha (11.13 per cent), Nagpur (10.31 per cent), Amravati (5.97 per cent), Yavatmal (4.09 per cent) and Vidarbha region (5.74 per cent) where as growth rate of production for Washim district was negatively significant. The district wise compound growth rates of productivity in Vidarbha during 2001-02 to 2020-21 was shown in below Table 3.

Table 3-Growth rates of productivity cotton in different districts in Vidarbha (2001-02 to 2020-21)

District	Period-I	Period-II	Overall
Buldhana	7.78*	0.94	1.65
Akola	10.84*	4.59	5.03**
Washim	9.32*	7.34	4.24*
Amravati	11.15**	1.76	6.87**
Yavatmal	11.25	-0.53	2.85
Amravati Division	10.52**	1.60	4.01**
Wardha	4.82*	7.31	5.05**
Nagpur	4.38*	8.97*	5.03**
Bhandara	-	-	-
Gondia	-	-	-
Chandrapur	9.29*	4.11	5.32**
Gadchiroli	-	-	-
Nagpur Division	5.43*	6.90	5.00**
Vidarbha	7.89**	4.47	4.59**

Note: ** Significance at 1 % level, * significance 5% level.

It could be seen from Table 3 that, during period I, the growth rate of productivity of cotton was highest in Amravati (12.33 per cent), followed by Akola (10.84 per cent), Washim (9.32 per cent), Chandrapur (9.29 per cent) and Buldhana(7.78 per cent) respectively. As for as Vidarbha is concerned the growth rate of productivity under cotton was positive (7.89 per cent) & significant. During Period II the

growth rate of cotton productivity for all the district and Vidarbha as a whole was non-significant. At overall 20 years the compound growth rate of productivity for cotton was positive and significant for Amravati (6.87 per cent), Chandrapur (5.32 per cent), Wardha (5.05 per cent), Akola & Nagpur (5.03 per cent), and Vidarbha region (4.59 per cent) and found significant.

One should not be obvious of instability by taking the growth rate only, because the growth rate will explain only the rate of growth over the period, whereas instability judge, whether the growth performance is stable or unstable for the period for the pertinent variable. The simple coefficient of variation (CV) often contains the trend component and thus overestimates the level of instability in the time series data

characterized by long term trend. To overcome this problem, this study used the instability index given by Cuddy Della Valle, which corrects the coefficient of variation. District wise Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index of area of cotton in Vidarbha was estimated and presented in Table 4

Table 4 : Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index of area of Cotton in different districts in Vidarbha (2001-02 to 2020-21)

Districts	Cotton (CDVII)		
	Period I	Period II	Overall
Buldhana	0.87	1.40	1.52
Akola	0.33	0.63	0.80
Washim	1.08	3.79	2.08
Amravati	1.68	0.85	2.16
Yavatmal	1.14	0.55	1.73
Amravati Division	0.72	0.00	0.99
Wardha	3.45	0.61	0.53
Nagpur	1.40	0.70	2.20
Bhandara	-	-	-
Gondia	-	-	-
Chandrapur	2.34	0.99	15.02
Gadchilori	-	-	-
Nagpur Division	2.46	0.68	4.50
Vidarbha	0.96	0.46	3.25

It is seen from Table 4 that, during period I Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index of area of cotton was lowest in Akola district (0.33 per cent) and highest in Wardha and Chandrapur district (3.45 and 2.34 per cent respectively). As a whole Vidarbha recorded low instability i.e. 0.96 per cent. During period II, the CDVII of area of cotton was lowest in Yavatmal district (0.55 per cent) and highest in Washim district

(3.79 per cent). As a whole Vidarbha recorded low instability i.e. 0.46 per cent. At overall period the CDVII of area of cotton was lowest in Wardha district (0.53 per cent) and highest in Chandrapur district (15.02 per cent). As a whole Vidarbha recorded 3.25 per cent. District wise Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index of production of cotton in Vidarbha was estimated and presented in Table 5.

Table 5 : Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index of production of Cotton in different districts in Vidarbha (2001-02 to 2020-21)

Districts	Cotton (CDVII)		
	Period I	Period II	Overall
Buldhana	2.53	5.31	4.67
Akola	3.29	3.12	3.25
Washim	4.27	6.53	5.00
Amravati	2.03	3.60	3.46
Yavatmal	3.19	0.00	4.31
Amravati Division	2.42	3.51	3.75
Wardha	3.45	2.90	1.86
Nagpur	2.08	2.96	3.53
Bhandara	-	-	-
Gondia	-	-	-
Chandrapur	2.03	3.08	12.17
Gadchilori	-	-	-
Nagpur Division	2.30	2.77	4.22
Vidarbha	2.16	3.06	4.80

It is seen from Table 5 that, during period I Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index of production of cotton was lowest in Amravati district (2.03 per cent) and highest in Washim (4.27) and Akola district (3.29) per cent respectively. As a whole Vidarbha recorded 2.16 per cent instability. During period II, the CDVII of production of cotton was lowest in Nagpur district (2.96 per cent) and highest in Washim district (6.53 per cent). As a whole Vidarbha recorded 3.06 per cent instability

At overall period the CDVII of production of cotton was lowest in Wardha district (1.86 per cent) and highest in Chandrapur and Akola district (12.17 and 5.00 per cent respectively). As a whole Vidarbha recorded 4.80 per cent instability. District wise Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index of productivity of cotton in Vidarbha was estimated and presented in Table 6

Table 6 : Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index of Productivity of Cotton in different districts in Vidarbha (2001-02 to 2020-21)

Cotton (CDVII)			
Districts	Period I	Period II	Overall
Buldhana	2.36	5.21	4.31
Akola	3.24	3.02	3.34
Washim	4.21	4.57	4.39
Amravati	2.24	3.97	3.57
Yavatmal	2.85	3.71	4.85
Amravati Division	2.34	3.65	3.33
Wardha	1.82	2.70	2.64
Nagpur	1.21	2.99	2.50
Bhandara	-	-	-
Gondia	-	-	-
Chandrapur	2.35	2.92	20.88
Gadchilori	-	-	-
Nagpur Division	1.49	2.66	3.14
Vidarbha	1.74	2.91	2.68

It is seen from Table 6 that, during period I Cuddy Della Valle Instability Index of productivity of cotton was lowest in Nagpur district (1.21 per cent) and highest in Washim and Akola district (4.21 and 3.24 per cent respectively). As a whole Vidarbha recorded 1.74 per cent instability. During period II, the CDVII of productivity of cotton was lowest in Wardha district (2.70 per cent) and highest in Buldhana district (5.21 per cent). As a whole Vidarbha recorded 2.91 per cent

instability. At overall period the CDVII of productivity of cotton was lowest in Nagpur district (2.50 per cent) and highest in Chandrapur and Yavatmal district (20.88 and 4.85 per cent respectively). As a whole Vidarbha recorded 2.68 per cent instability. Per cent contribution of area, yield and their interaction for increasing production of cotton in Vidarbha was estimated and presented in Table 7

Table 7: Per cent contribution of area, yield and their interaction for increasing production of cotton in Vidarbha

Sr.No.	District	Particulars	Period I	Period II	Overall
1	Buldhana	Area Effect	11.9	-43.6	-5.4
		Yield Effect	77.14	181.32	113.99
		Intr. Infect	11.00	-37.69	-8.60
2	Akola	Area Effect	-72.46	-20.2	-42.7
		Yield Effect	237.83	128.02	207.62
		Intr. Infect	-65.37	-7.78	-64.87
3	Washim	Area Effect	-80.72	294.7	890.7
		Yield Effect	286.24	-571.69	-3561.66
		Intr. Infect	-105.52	376.96	2770.98
4	Amravati	Area Effect	-77.1	27.2	-6.6
		Yield Effect	281.32	49.43	125.34
		Intr. Infect	-104.26	23.40	-18.73
5	Yavatmal	Area Effect	6.4	-22.9	5.6
		Yield Effect	85.28	124.90	87.17
		Intr. Infect	8.35	-2.00	7.26
6	Amravati Division	Area Effect	-12.0	-5.0	-9.9
		Yield Effect	126.03	107.29	127.09
		Intr. Infect	-14.02	-2.31	-17.20
7	Wardha	Area Effect	28.8	47.7	18.5
		Yield Effect	56.01	38.30	50.22
		Intr. Infect	15.16	13.98	31.31
8	Nagpur	Area Effect	1.4	21.5	17.5
		Yield Effect	97.78	50.44	41.59
		Intr. Infect	0.85	28.06	40.91
9	Chndrapur	Area Effect	27.1	39.8	19.7
		Yield Effect	48.05	38.89	31.88
		Intr. Infect	24.85	21.35	48.42
10	Nagpur Division	Area Effect	25.3	35.2	19.2
		Yield Effect	59.30	44.14	41.73
		Intr. Infect	15.43	20.64	39.06
11	Vidarbha	Area Effect	-4.6	14.7	2.9
		Yield Effect	109.42	77.53	91.66

	Intr. Infect	-4.78	7.78	5.46
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It was evident from the Table 7 that, in case of cotton, during period I yield effect was the most responsible factor for changing production in all the district of Vidarbha region. Highest yield effect was observed in Washim district (286.24 per cent), followed by Amravati district (281.32 per cent), and in Akola (237.83 per cent.) In Vidarbha yield effect was most responsible factor for changing cotton production i.e. 109.42 per cent, whereas the area effect and interaction effect was negative at -4.6 per cent and -4.78 per cent respectively, Hence yield effect indicate that, the yield has been playing a driving force in differential form of cotton production.

During Period II, it was observed that, yield effect of Buldhana district i.e. 181.32 per cent playing a major role in changing production of cotton and area effect was negative -43.6 per cent and interaction effect was also negative -37.69 per cent per annum. In this period yield effect was the most responsible factor for change in production for all the district except Washim district (-571.69 per cent)

At overall period, the yield effect was most responsible factor for change in production for five district which included Buldhana, Akola,

Table 8 : Estimated coefficient of acreage response function of cotton

Particular	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat
Intercept	5956.93	3116.37	1.9115
Area t-1 (x1)	0.4905	0.2145	2.2863**
FHP t-1 (x2)	0.4967	1.1385	0.4363
MSP t (x3)	0.2688	1.0987	0.24465
WSP t-1 (x4)	-0.0848	0.438	-0.1937
Price Risk FHP(x5)	1.1824	62.4495	0.0189
Pr Risk MSP (x6)	-53.0863	52.7711	-1.0060
Price Risk WP (x7)	-14.493	37.0839	-0.3908
Yield Risk (x8)	-10.5792	22.4741	-0.4707
R ²	0.751		
Adjusted R Square	0.5695		
DF	19		

It was revealed from table 8 that, the lagged area was found to be positively influential factors in the farmers decision regarding area allocation to cotton and found significant at 1 per cent level of significant in Vidarbha region which indicated lesser rigidity in the adjustment of area under cotton. The coefficient of farm harvest price and wholesale prices were very less i.e. 0.4967 and -0.0848 in Vidarbha respectively and it was non significant which implies less and negative relationship between the variation in the hectareage of cotton and farm harvest prices. It implies that prices had not shown any impact in the increase on area of cotton in the study period. The Yield risk variable

Amravati, Yavatmal and Wardha district i.e. 113.99 per cent, 207.62 per cent, 125.34 per cent, 87.17 per cent, 50.22 per cent respectively. The area effect was most responsible factor for change in production for Nagpur district (41.59 per cent) in remaining district interaction effect is most responsible factor. Regarding Vidarbha as a whole area effect is most responsible factor for change in cotton production i.e. 91.66 per cent whereas area effect and interaction effect were 2.9 per cent and 5.46 per cent respectively. Hence, in both Priod I and Period II, yield effect was responsible for increasing cotton production in Vdarbha. Acreage response functions were fitted to examine the effect of price on farmer's decision in allocating the area of paddy in Vidarbha. The actual area in the current year was express as a linear function of one year lagged area, one year lagged farm harvest prices, one year lagged MSP and one year lagged wholesale prices. The regression coefficient of these explanatory variables are presented in Table 8.

was incorporated in the model to gauge the impact of risk over the variation in the hectareage under cotton. The coefficient of variable had a negative and statistically non-significant response over a period of study. It was also recorded that, regression coefficient of price risk variables or factors were negative, it indicated that, farmers were not able to bear the risk. The value of coefficient of determination was 0.75 indicates that, variable included in the model explain most of the variation in the area under cotton in the study period. Table 9 indicates the comparison between producers price, cost of production and MSP of cotton

Table 9 Comparison between producer price, cost of production and MSP of cotton

Sr. No	Items	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21	2021-22	Average
1	Producer Price (Rs./Qtl.)	4822.26	5406.67	5052.85	5511.21	3663.11	4891.22
2	Cost of Production (Rs./Qtl)						
a	at cost A	3282.65	3366.844	3547.699	3626.601	3663.11	3497.381
b	at cost C	4996.47	5101.68	5133.09	5334.05	6040.12	5321.082
3	MSP (Rs./Qtl)	4320	5450	5550	5825	6025	5434
4	Parity Between Cost & MSP						
	at cost A	1037.35	2083.16	2002.30	2198.40	2361.89	1936.62
	at cost C	-676.47	348.32	416.91	490.95	-15.12	112.918
5	% of producer price over MSP	111.63	99.20	91.04	94.61	60.80	90.01

It was observed that, Farmers were receiving less price as compare to MSP. The parity between cost of production and MSP price was range

from Rs. -15.12 to 490.95 during last six years, Hence it is necessary to fixed MSP on the cost of production for the cotton.

Conclusion

At overall level the compound growth rate of area of cotton for Vidarbha region is positive and significant. The compound growth rate of production of cotton is positive and significant at overall level for Vidarbha region. At overall level for Vidarbha region area, the CDVII 3.25 per cent instability. At overall level for Vidarbha region production Vidarbha recorded 4.80 per cent instability. At overall level for Vidarbha region productivity, Vidarbha recorded 2.68 per cent instability. Vidarbha as a whole yield effect is most responsible factor for change in cotton production i.e. 91.66 per cent where as area effect and interaction effect were 2.9 per cent and 5.46 per cent respectively.

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